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Governance and the Local Integration
of Migrants and Europe's Refugees

Gender Dynamics across Reception and Integration in Italy

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Executive Summary

- In Italy, a series of reforms have been carried out in order to introduce concrete measures to stop violence against women.
- Some legislative measures have represented significant steps forward, including legislation against stalking, laws requiring allocation of financial resources and an extensive network of victim support services, special remunerated leave for workers who are victims of gender-based violence and protection of orphans affected by domestic crime.
- Regarding governance, integration measures are implemented by two ministries: The Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, and the Department for Equal Opportunities.
- Local governance is entrusted to the regions, which provide specific programmes and interact with the municipalities and prefectures, which function as guarantors of first reception projects (CAS) and integrated reception for migrant children and refugees (SIPROIMI).
- In Calabria, integration from a gender perspective is largely entrusted to dialogue between local administrations and third sector organisations, which manage reception projects, participate in the allocation of specific funds managed by the Region and execute reception programmes.
- In terms of housing, work integration and language learning, the local integration system is fully interconnected and linked to the SIPROIMI territorial projects and CAS centres, as well as to initiatives of the CPIA and employment offices.
- The prevention and management of victims of trafficking and gender-based violence is entrusted to the national reception system.
- Despite the progress achieved in promoting women's rights, gender equality is still met with resistance and lacks specialisation in dedicated staff; this is often addressed only in terms of family and maternity policies.

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I. Gender Dynamics in Migrant Integration: Legal and Methodological Aspects

According to the Gender Equality Index (EIGE, 2019) Italy is ranked 14th in the European Union compared to the Gender Equality Indicators. Overall, the score is about 4 points lower than the European level. Nevertheless, Italy is progressing towards gender equality significantly faster than the other Member States. Its ranking has improved by 12 points since 2005. However, this progress should not overlook the gender inequalities that remain in social and political participation (47.6 points) and work (63.1 points). The most positive findings are those relating to the health care and education ratings (88.7 and +7.1 points, respectively).

For the purposes of this report, two methodological approaches were used. For the analysis of SGBV, four qualitative interviews were conducted with stakeholders on with violence against refugees' men and women (e.g. sexual and family violence; gender-based violence toward LGBTQIA refugees; trafficking); the stakeholders were selected based on their expertise in the field and contacted through associations and institutions to which they belong. In this case, semi-structured qualitative interviews were used, and were organised around main themes aimed at highlighting the main dimensions of the SGBV, good practices to question, and arising critical issues. As for the other sections, no new interviews were conducted; however, the 40 interviews conducted for the other work packages have been re-read through a gender perspective. The latter is a methodology that focuses on the points of view and experiences of people, considering their gender identity, highlighting both the gender imbalance and specific problems in the evaluation – in this case, of the policies and practices affecting refugees.

Image 1: Riace, Calabria |
Source: www.vita.it

I.1 National strategies and legal framework

One of the first examples of the Italian strategy that can help to analyse migrants from a gender perspective is the National Code of Equal Opportunities and the laws that apply the European Union directives on equal opportunities and equal treatment, especially in terms of employment and job placement. As a result of these regulations, direct and indirect discrimination is defined and prohibited, and a network of equal opportunities consultants is created that provides legal assistance to women (for all legal situations) affected by discrimination. Family law recognises perfect equality between men and women and gives the same rights to children born inside and outside of marriage.

On 28 October 2010, the Ministry for Equal Opportunities approved the first National Plan against gender-based violence and stalking (a crime that was not codified in Italian legislation before 2009), followed by the creation of Law no. 119/2013 against femicide. Indeed, thanks to the introduction in 2009 of the law against stalking and those violent and persecutory behaviour forcing the victim to change his or her life conduct, the legislation regarding 'Urgent provisions for safety and the contrast of gender violence', and the judicial protection and support to victims

Image 2: OSCAD officer |
Source: www.interno.it

have been strengthened. This has also given the opportunity for migrants who were victims of this form of gender violence to apply for residence permits for humanitarian reasons.

This legislation, revised by Law n.69/2019 on the protection of victims of domestic and gender violence, comes entirely within the framework set out by the Istanbul Convention of 2011. Data collection and control is carried out by the Observatory for Security against Discriminatory Acts (OSCAD), a joint police/carabinieri inter-force structure. The Observatory facilitates the submission of claims regarding discriminatory acts constituting a crime, in order to bypass under-reporting and, therefore, encourage detection of discrimination-based crimes. It:

- a) keeps relations with associations and institutions, both public and private, involved in the anti-discrimination policy;
- b) monitors and analyses data from the alerts received or available in police databases;
- c) promotes professional training of police officers;
- d) activates institutional collaborations at national and international levels;
- e) is involved in activities designed to create and disseminate social communications about OSCAD through the media and the police territorial branches, and takes part in public information and awareness campaigns, including in schools.

In any case, the notification of a discriminatory act to OSCAD is no substitute for a crime reported to the police. In the regional territories, local prefectures promote information and awareness-raising initiatives to fight gender-based violence as soon as it arises through: training in schools; training courses for social and healthcare workers to improve initial reception; forms of collaboration with local authorities and associations to strengthen reception and support for victims; and task forces and working groups to plan initiatives and disseminate best practices.

According to the first report on the implementation of the CoE Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence in Italy (GREVIO, 2019), these legislative measures represented significant steps forward in supporting and promoting an extensive network of victim support services, in particular through the allocation of financial resources. Two other legislative instruments were considered particularly innovative: Legislative Decree no. 80/2015, which provides for special paid leave for female workers affected by gender-based violence, and Law no. 4/2018, which contains extensive measures to protect orphans of domestic crime victims.

However, while recognising the progress achieved to promote women's rights in Italy, attention must be given to how gender equality still faces resistance in Italy; there is a growing trend of reinterpreting and re-orienting the notion of gender equality in terms of family and maternity policies. With regard to asylum rights, the same report underlines that the absence of effective vulnerability screening procedures, which do not allow the correct identification of victims, can lead to expulsion or repatriation – in violation of the non-refoulement clause. Recent policies aimed at stopping sea rescues and strengthening the deterrence of potential migrants, combined with the closure of Italian ports for migrants arriving with rescue boats at sea, are increasing the risk of repatriation in the future.

1.2 Approach to the gender integration of migrants in Calabria

Among the twenty Italian regions, Calabria ranks thirteenth for the number of non-Italian residents. In 2018, there was an increase of 4,584 people compared to the previous year. There are 113,078 migrants living in Calabria, 42.1% of whom are women (IDOS, 2019). This increase was mainly a result of the local population decrease, which between 2017 and 2018 decreased by more than 14,000 residents. Splitting the two groups of Calabrian residents (i.e. Italian citizens and immigrants), Italy's population has decreased significantly over an eight-year period (2008-2016), while the number of immigrants has increased.

Regarding the framework of local integration, Regional Law no. 18 of 12 June 2009 is the most important legislative reference, supplemented by the latest and most recent amendments, such as Regional Law no. 13 of 16 May 2018. In Italy, it is the regional government that promotes the integrated regional reception system that supports the socio-economic integration of refugees, asylum seekers and holders of subsidiary or humanitarian protection. The planning instrument for the proposed measures is the so-called Regional Plan, which is based on:

- a) A three-year perspective;
- b) The evolution in the reception of asylum seekers and refugees both in the region and in Italy;
- c) The regulatory measures adopted at national level and within the EU.

The overall performance of the actions carried out in the three-year period of implementation of the plan are evaluated by the regional administration, which takes into account the report of the Committee of Guarantors, a board of experts and academics that supervises the activities of the dedicated health, social and welfare structures, recommends the adoption of specific measures in case of omissions by the authorities, and, if it detects situations of risk or damage to individuals, reports them to the appropriate authorities.

The strategy of regional integration policies, within a gender perspective, are based on the guidelines of the Interior Ministry and Equal Opportunities, as well as the multi-level management entrusted to the Extraordinary Reception Centres (CAS) and centres for refugees and unaccompanied minors (SIPROIMI, SPRAR). In fact, Calabria can only

operate in support (e.g. economic, financial) and has identified guidelines for the drafting and implementation of temporary policies and interventions during the period 2019-2021 by:

- a) creating conditions for an early start of the integration process since the first reception, in particular by including language teaching and cultural guidance;
- b) implementing integration services in all structures, with special attention to the CAS, especially in those cases where such services play an important role as second reception centres;
- c) providing calls for proposals to manage reception centres for skilled professionals able to work in multicultural contexts and social mediation, ensuring particular attention is given to situations of vulnerability, gender differences and family groups.

Therefore, according to Resolution no. 242 of 07 June 2019, most of the actions on integration and gender policies are referred to the municipalities as coordinators of local reception projects, and to third sector organisations as promoters of municipal policies.

1.3 Migrant organisations and national decision-makers

Most of our information on women refugees and asylum seekers' public participation is based on informal communication and interviews, as there are no specific data in relation to this, especially at local level. Concerning the latter, while initiatives enhancing the participation of migrant women and men have been and are easily developed, there are few experiences focused on the participation of women refugee and asylum seekers.

In general, this depends on the demographic characteristics of the refugee and asylum seeker population in Italy and Calabria, among whom men are more represented than women. Moreover, women refugees and asylum seekers have usually migrated together with their families, and in this case, the responsibility for the representation in the public sphere is taken by family men, usually the husbands. Recently, there has been an increase in refugee and asylum seeker women migrating alone, especially those coming from Nigeria, that are a particularly vulnerable group, as they are often victims of trafficking. As such they are usually prevented from expressing a widely understood political presence. In some interviews, NGOs workers in the area of Lamezia Terme and Reggio Calabria note that even women fleeing trafficking are unlikely to participate in the public and political spheres because they have an absolute distrust in the institutions. They also underline that in some cases where churches are involved in working with women refugees, this may be an easier means of reaching them.

Image 3: Rosarno, Reggio Calabria
| Source: openmigration.org

A relevant issue affecting women refugees and asylum seekers' participation is the degree of specialisation of NGO workers working with them: a gender-blind approach prevents women participation as well as the introduction of empowerment processes in general. The scarce presence of refugee women and asylum seekers in the spaces of public and political participation determines the impossibility of exercising a direct advocacy on the policies related to the processes of reception and integration of asylum seekers and refugees, which are often subjected to and received as normative elements that influence life's possibilities and choices.

2. Gender Dynamics and Housing Policies

In Italy, housing policies supporting applicants for international protection and refugees are lacking at national level, and if observed from a gender perspective remain at a very basic level. There is a considerable gap between what is required by the few regulations and what can be achieved in practice. In this regard, it is important to remember that women applicants for international protection and refugees have specific reception needs, both in the departure and arrival countries.

Locations where they can be accommodated are often overcrowded, promiscuous and lacking protected spaces. This exposes women and girls to multiple risks: suffering further violence, being sexually exploited, and experiencing inadequate health care. Paradoxically, women who escape violence and persecution come to reception centres that are almost as dangerous. Every small step can be complicated (Pascale, 2016, 84) inside and outside reception centres. The search for 'accommodation can be difficult and precisely for this reason single refugee women remain more frequently and for longer periods in emergency accommodation than men' (Tognetti, 2016).

2.1 National housing policies: a gender perspective

According to the relevant European directives, special arrangements are made for women asylum seekers and refugees. For example, Article 7 of Legislative Decree no. 142/2015 states, with regard to reception centres, that applicants must be guaranteed separate accommodation and respect for gender differences. Where possible, the unity of the family unit must be preserved.

According to Article 10 of the same decree, private life, including gender differences and the protection of the physical and mental health of the applicants must be ensured in these reception centres. Theoretically, according to Article 11, also in extraordinary reception centres (CAS) the 'essential reception needs' must respect the principle of protecting women, alone or with children, from men. Special attention, according to Article 17 of Legislative Decree no. 142/2015, must be dedicated to vulnerable individuals, including pregnant women and people who have been identified as having been victims of torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence linked to sexual orientation or gender identity, as well as victims of genital mutilation.

However, the already fragile Italian public system for the reception and protection of asylum seekers and refugees (SPRAR) was radically changed at the end of 2018. Legislative Decree no. 113/2018 (converted into Law no. 132/2018) has modified the organisational structure and aims of SPRAR, now renamed SIPROIMI. This reform, viewed from a gender perspective and in terms of the structures in place to receive applicants for international protection, appears to be very problematic. The beneficiaries of the public reception system are no longer applicants, but only holders of international protection, unaccompanied minors, or owners of residence permits for 'special cases'. In this last category there are also 'victims of domestic violence' (Art. 18 bis, legislative decree 286/98); this protection is granted to the migrant person when physical, psychological, or sexual violence occurs within the family. Victims of domestic violence, almost exclusively women, will therefore remain within the SIPROIMI circuit and will be able to benefit from – when entering, in itinere and exiting – the housing orientation.

With regard to the victims of trafficking, however, which is often combined with the need for international protection, this status has certainly been affected by the 2018 regulatory reform. Trafficked persons seeking international protection are not placed in the SPRAR-SIPROIMI but in the Extraordinary Reception Centres (CAS), conceived as 'parking structures' (Schiavone, 2019, 170). Women trafficked for sexual exploitation or other purposes are the first victims of the reform of the reception system. For the first reception centres and CAS, the new contract terms and conditions, approved in November 2018, provided a drastic reduction, and often a real exclusion, of all individual services. Only the basic facilities (accommodation and meals) are provided, with no specific reception measures for vulnerable cases.

In addition to new and existing problems with the housing conditions in the first and second reception period, there are also problems in subsequent phases. These problematic situations increase when public authorities do not prepare adequate strategies and plans for housing. Individuals who are willing to rent apartments to applicants for international protection and/or refugees are becoming increasingly difficult to find. For refugee women this means living at risk of violence in overcrowded and often promiscuous environments with unfamiliar men. Women, if alone and with dependent minors, are mainly unable to earn adequate incomes to afford rent in areas with good quality schools and socio-health services once they leave the reception system. Segregation of residential accommodation certainly represents an obstacle to any integration process.

2.2 Best practice and networking system in Calabria

The empirical research was conducted in small and medium-sized urban centres located in three different provinces of Calabria. The small towns in the interior of Calabria have experienced a process of depopulation and social 'desertification' during the last few decades. Moreover, refugees' presence in the small municipalities of Calabria – especially with regard to women refugees (alone, as a single parental group, with their families) – reveals an important link between the re-construction of borders, citizenship and social innovation.

Within these municipalities that are experiencing depopulation and serious lack or absence of social services for minors and families, there are reception projects for single mothers, refugees' families and unaccompanied minors.

Our research was carried out in Riace, a village of 1,726 inhabitants in the Locride area, along the Ionian coast of Calabria, in the province of Catanzaro; Acquaformosa, a mountain town in the province of Cosenza, located in the Pollino area with 1,115 inhabitants and an Arbëreshë linguistic minority; Feroletto Antico, a town of 2,137 inhabitants in the province of Catanzaro; Gioiosa Ionica, a town of 7,105 inhabitants located in the Locride area, near the metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria; Villa San Giovanni, with a population of 13,524 inhabitants, in the province of Reggio Calabria and overlooking Messina Strait.

Image 4: Acquaformosa, Calabria |
Source: assmatrangolo.it

In 2012, five (almost completely uninhabited) buildings located in the historical centre of Acquaformosa were recovered with the Integrated Local Development Projects 'Contrasting Depopulation' and 'Linguistic Minorities' (Operational Programme Calabria ERDF 2007-2013), and were later granted by the municipality for the activity and reception of young refugees and local families. The experiences collected suggest a general lack of opposition from local communities to host first, and then integrate, women with children or families. In Feroletto Antico, a municipality of just 800 inhabitants, there has been an extraordinary Reception Centre in place for single mothers since 2016.

The centre is coordinated by the Cooperativa Progetto Sud of Lamezia Terme, which has consolidated expertise in the social welfare aspects related to the reception of refugees. This experience represents an example of best practice for the integration of refugee women living in an area strongly affected by the presence of an Emergency Identification Centre, and characterised by urban degradation and social marginality. The Secondary Reception Centre has become a meeting place, open to continuous visits, where women feel at home. It is interesting to note how, in the very early stages, there emerged:

...the stereotypes about Nigerian women... all whores... the ex-nursery turned into a whorehouse... then we involved a group of 15 people who offered to be godmothers or godfathers at the christenings of the hosts' children... Some of them, voluntarily, give Italian lessons... but now these women are leaving, and we cannot include them in the projects carried out by the cooperative... With this group of godmothers, we are having a meeting with the psychologists to understand the experience and prepare them to be separated (Int. n.6).

When interviewing an operator of Feroletto's CAS about the concept of home for a refugee woman, the answer received was:

If I think about my experience, the people I met... there is not only one answer, because for many of them the journey never ends, that always terrified me on one side, and on the other side it's a beautiful horizon to follow... to feel you never arrived in any place... to have no roots anywhere... If I think about the women when they talk about the CAS, they call it home, they say "but don't you come home tomorrow?" (Int. No. 10).

3. Gender Dynamics and Labour Market Integration

In Italy, the presence of non-EU nationals is characterised by a significant incidence of irregular flows despite the three regularisation settlements. Considering non-regular immigration control mechanisms, the percentage of the immigrant population is more relevant than the official number of regular ones – 5.144 million (ISTAT, 2019) – especially in regions like Calabria, where landings and arrivals from the sea can be expected. Unfortunately, there is no single unequivocal estimate of the population irregularly present in the country.

According to the latest statistical data on migrants in the Italian labour market (ANPAL, 2019), there is a good percentage of employed women from third countries in Calabria (8,428) compared to the local population, especially in the middle age groups (30-49, at 66%). Even an overall analysis of the migrant population living in the region offers a highly descriptive image of the phenomenon: most notably, the presence of women who are alone or far from their families accessing work (46%) emerges, as opposed to single-parent individuals (12%) or families with children (33%).

The sectors in which there is a presence of migrant and refugee women are: unskilled manual work (58%), collective services and personal care (62%), local commerce (14%) and agriculture (8%). The typology is mainly subordinate, but there is an increased number of women in self-employment (11%). However, on a national scale, there is a very high percentage of young migrant women (37%) – aged between 16 and 24 – who do not work, study or are in training (FRA, 2019). These data perfectly match the situation in Calabria.

3.1 Labour market integration: a semi-decentralised governance

While the processes of social inclusion of asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection face a complex and fragmented labour market, the long-standing problems of undeclared and irregular work based on the labour exploitation of vulnerable population groups exist.

Our research (Loprieno, Elia, Di Maio, 2019) has already underlined that the governance of public policies on the employment inclusion and integration of migrants in Italy is entrusted to the Directorate General for Immigration

and Integration Policies of the Labour Ministry. The operational branch of these actions is the so-called employment centres (CPI), which are public structures coordinated by the regions and are responsible for encouraging the matching of supply and demand for employment with initiatives and interventions of active labour policies. Employment centre activities are aimed at all residents in the region, both unemployed and workers at risk of unemployment, as well as occupied workers in search of new employment. Since 1 July 2018, Calabria offers 15 employment centres (structured on a provincial basis), in addition to 25 offices and local information points relating to the CPI.

These are the places where, essentially, the Ministry of Labour and Equal Opportunities has implemented work inclusion actions from a gender perspective, based on the government level. However, many initiatives are also devolved to the private sector, within the national system of first and second reception (CAS, SIPROIMI). In this area, although the percentage of beneficiaries is limited, integration policies have more impact, especially in terms of support to migrants towards self-reliance.

Regarding Calabria's situation, it is important to underline how the experience of SIPROIMI (and previously, of SPRAR) informs the beneficiaries about the risks generated by the missed or illegal job insertion: teams from the analysed centres (Cosenza, Catanzaro, Lamezia Terme, Villa S. Giovanni) carry out training on a daily basis informing migrants about the importance of working legally and the detection of undeclared work, focusing on any periods of beneficiary absence from the reception structures, especially if this coincides with seasonal work cycles in agriculture or when they are looking for a job or for a placement interview.

This problem, in the contexts analysed, concerns above all women, who are forced to leave the integration process faster because they cannot manage the internship/family/work relationship or because they have easier access to certain job positions, even if not always legally. However, out of more than 800,000 regular domestic workers, the foreign component represents almost 70% of the total workforce (IDOS, 2019):

Women do not attend because they find work more easily, as caregivers and as domestic workers, and often their parents provide care for their children. [...] We're trying to create a course to allow these women to attend even for a few hours per day. (Cultural Mediator n.2, Catanzaro).

3.2 Labour integration policies and against illegal exploitation

According to the entry flow planning system for non-seasonal work, there is a significant amount of illegal immigration in Italy: at the end of 2018 there were about 530,000 non-EU citizens with invalid residence permits, of whom between 150,000 and 200,000 were employed illegally as domestic workers, caregivers and babysitters (IDOS, 2019). In Calabria, this also occurs in the food and agriculture sectors, where the gender perspective becomes absolutely relevant. It should be noted that women – even if to a lesser extent than men – can still be victims of

exploitative practices such as the *Caporalato*, an illegal form of workforce recruitment by local micro-criminality organisations, usually in the agricultural sector.

Due to the spread of the *Caporalato* in the agriculture sector, in February 2020 the Italian government adopted a series of actions to counter this. For this purpose, the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies defined the first ‘Three-year plan to contrast labour exploitation in agriculture and the *Caporalato* (2020-2022)’. It provides for an implementation strategy articulated in three different phases. A first phase of analysis is followed by emergency interventions in the most critical areas (in which Calabria is included) followed by a system action covering the whole national territory. This last phase is based on four priority areas: prevention; vigilance and contrast; protection and assistance; and social and labour reintegration.

Image 5: Rosarno, Calabria | Source: www.agi.it

While this programme of public policies is implemented, it is important to highlight the work being carried out by the SIPROIMI network in Calabria to increase so-called ‘social agriculture’ experiences, an innovative approach based on the combination of two distinct concepts: multifunctional agriculture and social/therapeutic-assistance services at local level (SPRAR/SIPROIMI, 2019). Within this integration action, several collaborations between SPRAR/SIPROIMI projects and social agricultural companies or cooperatives (e.g. Lamezia Terme) have been created, with the mutual aim of promoting the social and working inclusion of asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection through the strengthening of their skills. In this network, public and private stakeholders are involved in various steps and operate by sharing the paths to be activated:

- a) public authorities (municipal social services and other services such as technical offices, employment centres, health services);
- b) private and social stakeholders (social agricultural companies or cooperatives, third sector associations);
- c) women in various capacities, as direct beneficiaries;
- d) local citizens, as indirect beneficiaries.

While these are valuable, they are individual and often limited local actions based on the foresight and concrete action of local administrations as well as third sector associations. According to the interviews, especially in Cosenza and Catanzaro, it was still very difficult for women to have easy access to employment, especially in terms of skill awareness and family relationship impact – not only for refugee women but also for the longest-integrated women in a mixed family unit.

Graph 1: Calabria - Migrants' job offer in a gender perspective (July 2019) |
Source: ANPAL Servizi S.P.A., www.anpal.gov.it

We understood that many times mothers come and, after a short time, husbands have to come to understand, to check where their wives go, and to see who is in the centre. They have to check that no other men are there. This also happens with mixed couples. We have had cases of Italians coming here to check whether the wife was really only with other women. (Cultural mediator no. 1, Cosenza)

In other words, we realized this: maybe the gender difference isn't outdated. It's obsolete for us, but, indeed, in Calabria where we live it is not true [...] and we must not underestimate a right that we we've got, never underestimate it, we've got to keep our fist firmly in place. (Educator no. 2, Cosenza)

4. Gender Dynamics and Educational Training

4.1 Italian language learning: is there a gender balance issue in language training courses?

The learning of the spoken Italian language equivalent to at least level A2 is an obligation provided for by the so-called 'integration agreement' (Article 4-bis of the TUI) in order to obtain any authorisation to stay for more than one year. It is, in fact, 'a path of compulsory integration' introduced by legislation (Law no. 94/2009). One way to acquire knowledge of the Italian language is to attend the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA), a type of autonomous school institution, usually organised on a provincial basis, in compliance with the regional school planning. With regard to the Reception System Protection System for International Protection Holders and Unaccompanied Foreign Minors (SIPROIMI ex-SPRAR), language learning and training are two of the objectives contained within the so-called 'reception pact' that make the Italian language one of the objectives to be achieved within a personalised integration project that SIPROIMI operators implement for refugees (Loprieno, Elia, Di Maio 2019).

The CPIAs are autonomous educational institutions; the regions play an essential role in the implementation of initiatives that promote the integration of adult migrants. These initiatives, however, are strongly linked to the availability of regional budgets, and to the political sensitivity of administrators towards migration issues, resulting in deep inequalities in the right to education in Italy (Biondi Dal Monte et al, 2017). Within this highly discretionary and localistic framework, the education of adults and young adults (aged 16 and over) with a migration background suffers from a process of educational segregation. This is a scenario that emerges clearly in the Calabrian CPIAs investigated in the province of Cosenza and Catanzaro from the ghettoisation of educational spaces in the urban suburbs; from the precariousness of the educational offer in language and social integration courses for foreigners (Italian L2) due to the variability of the number of teachers and learners; and the absence of specialised personnel such as psychologists and cultural mediators (Loprieno, Elia, Di Maio 2019).

As far as the Calabrian SIPROIMI projects are concerned, although specialised figures are present and initiatives for schooling and literacy are organised in a continuous and complementary way to the CPIA, the Italian L2 teacher is not always an integral part of the project team. This is mainly due to financial cuts and the general downsizing of the national protection reception system, both for the exclusion of applicants for international protection from the reception system and for the reduction in the number of places in the territorial reception circuit of the municipalities (Amnesty International 2019; Melting Pot 2019; Migrantes Foundation 2019). Within this context of educational marginality the gender issue becomes an additional barrier that is not answered within the language training policies, but rather in the institutional networks re-constructed territorially between intra and extra-educational environments: local actors and training institutions (the SIPROIMI projects and the Provincial Centres for Adult Education) that face the challenge of overcoming gender barriers in the access to education for refugee women.

4.2 Language training programmes challenge to gendered barriers in Calabria

Women in migration, particularly refugee women, make up a small percentage of the student population of the Calabrian CPIA. This figure contrasts with the trend towards the feminisation of migratory flows towards Italy and Calabria, a presence now widespread due to home care and care work (Ambrosini 2013), but in line with the percentage of arrivals of refugee women. UNHCR data show that in 2017 women accounted for only 12.6% of arrivals by sea in Europe and 11.2 in Italy (UNHCR 2017). However, the UNHCR (2018) points out that the arrival of women asylum seekers is a growing phenomenon which is also linked to trafficking for sexual and labour exploitation, as discussed in paragraph § 2.2 and § 3.2.

The low participation of refugee women in adult education courses, according to the reports of social workers of SIPROIMI projects and CPIA teachers, is explained by the discrimination experienced by refugee women in which gender intersects in complex ways with educational backgrounds, ethnicity and trauma.

Regarding educational backgrounds, the teachers and lecturers in the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) witness a process of ethnicisation of Italian language learning as L2. Migrant women, mainly from Eastern Europe (Russia, Estonia, Ukraine, Moldova), have an educational background and a level of autonomy that would make them active participants in school activities. Even among refugee women there is a geography of learning that would indicate a different educational background depending on their origin. For example, there is a difference between Syrian refugee women with a high level of education and women from West and Central Africa who are illiterate, yet have a strong ability to speak in several native languages:

They haven't been educated: they've been to Islamic school but don't know how to read or write in their mother tongue, so they didn't know the Latin alphabet. They speak various languages but can't write. (Teacher Int. n. 6)

Image 6: Multi-Purpose Centre for the Integration and Social Inclusion of Migrants of Cosenza | Source: www.quicosenza.it

The educational poverty matured in their place of origin penalises refugee women in particular compared to men (Dryden-Peterson, 2011). This intersects a serious condition of vulnerability, due to violence that is constant and variable, i.e. a continuous violence that takes different forms during the journey, from the moment they leave their country, in detention centres in Libya, during the crossing to the arrival in Europe (UNHCR 2011). Trauma and violence inevitably affect the psyche and health of refugee women, but this dimension is hardly perceived by public opinion and often remains in the background even in the first reception procedures.

An interview offered by the person in charge of the multidisciplinary Desk for support to victims of torture in Cosenza denounces that most of the activities of the Desk are dedicated to the emergence of this phenomenon. The commitment of the volunteers at the Desk is aimed at monitoring the Extraordinary Reception Centres without services dedicated to psychological support; at listening to refugee women who turn to the Desk spontaneously or because they are reported by other territorial reception projects. The Desk, managed by Kasbha, which was established with an agreement with Calabria, is in fact the only point of observation in southern Italy for the phenomenon of torture and, citing in agreement with the Provincial Health Authority of Cosenza, is governed by the work of volunteer doctors of a local association (AUSER Territorial Cosenza – Medical Outpatient Clinic Without Borders).

Image 7: Desk for support to victims of torture in Cosenza | Source: www.ausercosenza.it

These women, who are victims of violence and are often single mothers, do not benefit from educational places where teachers are unable to meet this particular audience's needs that range from the need to define personalised teaching activities to taking advantage of motivational paths for learning the Italian language. The experience of

trauma and violence raises a strong emotional barrier to language learning, and to this is added the embarrassment that comes from not knowing how to read and write – the inability to communicate.

The testimonies collected from the educators of the SIPROIMI system convey the emotional fragilities of single mothers placed in a system that 'privileges male-dominated 'public' activities over the activities of women, which take place largely in the 'private' sphere' (Fenster 1999). This aspect emerges from the difficulty in reconciling the care of children with the attendance of Italian language courses due in part to the absence of early childhood services in a context of high educational poverty (in Calabria, only 2.6% of children attend a public nursery [Save the Children 2019]), the logistical difficulties due to the absence of transport, and the distance of the CPIA from reception projects (Loprieno, Elia, Di Maio 2019).

In addition to gender barriers, however, it should be noted that the refusal of single mothers to attend L2 Italian language courses can become a precise choice that tends to deconstruct the binary depiction of the poor and vulnerable refugee woman (Kelly, 2000). An example is given by the testimonies of the social workers of the Multi-Purpose Centre for the Integration and Social Inclusion of Legal Immigrants of Cosenza who integrate with literacy activities the schooling hours held in the CPIA and welcome the children of refugee women who attend the centre. The women's refusal to attend the CPIA was followed by the setup of a service renewal process that incorporated a nursery service in the Multi-Purpose Centre building and laboratory activities to support language learning.

In this context, the refugee women learn Italian by reproducing their domestic environment: the cooking workshop; motherhood; taking care of their children, who attend the Centre's nursery. The cooking workshop works and creates this kind of relationship... they prefer to come to lessons here instead of going to the CPIA... staying near the nursery where their children are... (Social Worker n.2, Polifunzionale, Cosenza)

The practices implemented underscore an ongoing search for methods through which literacy teaching for migrant women can be incorporated into a broader process of 'raising awareness' that aims to support the integration of female refugees locally. Recognising the needs of women has paved the way for individualised assistance programmes. Incorporating gender along with other attributes of displaced persons will greatly enhance the type and quality of services provided. Furthermore, allowing refugee women to be active participants in education programmes will further integrate needs and responses.

5. Sexual and Gender Based Violence in Calabria

There is some aggregated data on SGBV against migrants and asylum seekers and refugees at national and local level, resulting from the lack of national homogeneous and adequately funded policies, and a certain reticence by the victims themselves to make a disclosure about the violence. However, there are some studies and research by

NGOs both at national and local level that focus on specific national or vulnerable groups (for example, Nigerian women victims of trafficking).

SGBV is a heterogeneous phenomenon, both qualitatively and with respect to the affected categories: it affects all refugees and asylum seekers – men and women – both in the country of departure, where specific SGBVs can be the same cause for departing, during the journey and in receiving countries, perpetuating situations of domestic violence, exposing refugees to prostitutions, and increasing the vulnerability of refugees and asylum seekers in reception centres, where violence can take place among migrants or between the latter's and reception centres' workers. Furthermore, refugees in Italy face considerable obstacles along the integration path, especially the most vulnerable: they are often at risk of exploitation and abuse, compromising the possibility of accessing services on an equal base with citizens.

5.1 The incidence of SGBV: a statistical and legal overview

According to the latest report of UNHCR (2019), based on meetings held with victims and reception centres' workers, the number of SGBV's cases reported by people arriving in Italy is very high: most women and minors arriving by sea survived sexual and gender-based violence, including sexual assault and rape, especially while travelling. These episodes mainly occur in Libya, but sexual harassment also occurs during the sea crossing (UN, 2016).

Many women are aware of the high risks along the way and have reported that they have used contraceptive injections to avoid unwanted pregnancies, which involves a specific health issue. In this sense, the exposure to sexually transmitted diseases following rape must also be considered. Furthermore, the number of women and girls, mainly from Nigeria and other Sub-Saharan countries, who are victims of trafficking and sexual exploitation has significantly increased in the past three years. The IOM estimates that around 80% of Nigerian women who arrived in Italy by sea in 2016 were potential victims of trafficking for the purpose of sexual exploitation in Italy or in other states of the European Union (OIM, 2020).

The number of child victims of trafficking (boys and girls) has also increased. An UNHCR assessment on child protection of September 2016 underlines that among unaccompanied children, survival sex for both boys and girls is as a frequent coping mechanism between refugees and asylum seekers. While mainly under-reported there is a growing incidence of SGBV on men, as highlighted by the Women's Refugee Commission in its March 2019 report 'More than One Million Pains" Sexual Violence Against Men and Boys on the Central Mediterranean Route to Italy' (Women's Refugee Commission, 2019).

There are no data on transgender people, apart from sporadic cases emerging in the work experience of some associations that highlight cases of specific violence against transgender people occurring in reception systems, which lack adequate knowledge to recognise and interact with transgender refugees. Homosexuality also represents

a specific factor of vulnerability to violence, especially in the case of men whose sexual orientation is particularly evident. Despite the fact that sexual orientation is often a reason to be recognised as a refugee, coming out is often difficult, as these people come from particularly homophobic contexts where homosexuality is socially and legally sanctioned.

This is particularly true considering the consequences of the law 113/2018 and 53/2019 extending the time spent in first reception centres. Homosexual refugees are forced to cohabit with communities of nationals within which prejudices and ostracism towards homosexuality are reproduced. This also nullifies the work of the few SPRAR projects specifically dedicated to the reception of LGBT refugees and asylum seekers. Regarding trafficking and sexual exploitation, according to the data collected by the IN.C.I.P.I.T. project it affects about 800-900 people in Calabria, mostly women, comprising a majority of Nigerian – a number increased in the last ten years due to the forced entry of Nigerian women in the regional street prostitution market (www.progettoincipit.com).

Image 8: 'Progetto Sud' Community involved in the INCIPIT project | Source: www.lameziainforma.it

5.2 SGBV in Calabria: prevention systems and risk reduction policies

In Italy, a series of policies and laws have recently been approved in relation to SGBV following the ratification in 2013 of the Council of Europe's 'Convention to Prevent and Combat Violence against Women and Domestic Violence' (Istanbul Convention) and of the Council of Europe's "Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Abuse' (Lanzarote Convention). In the same year, law 119/2013 was approved, introducing urgent rules on the safeguard and fight against SGBV, giving a special residence permit for foreign victims of domestic violence via Article 4.

In addition, the Italian Government has adopted three National Action Plans concerning SGBV: the 'National Plan against Gender-Based Violence and Stalking' in 2011, the 'Extraordinary Plan of Action against Sexual and Gender Violence 2015-2017' in 2014 and the 'National Strategic Plan to Combat Men's Violence Against Women 2017-2020', which is specifically committed to migrant, refugee and asylum seeker women.

Moreover, in 2016, the 'National Action Plan against Trafficking and Serious Exploitation of Human Beings' was issued. The plan is based on the 4 Ps of the Istanbul protocol (Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Partnership) and establishes new measures to improve the identification of victims of trafficking among migrants and asylum seekers, together with a specific National Referral Mechanism. Despite this improvement in the legislative framework, effective and efficient implementation is limited, mainly because of the lack of funds and specialised professionals. Furthermore, the legislation does not provide adequate funds and support to existing anti-violence centres and shelters that play a central role in supporting women. In general, the implementation of these policies is not homogeneous at national level and varies greatly between and within regions.

As the UNHCR reports points out, there is no adequate, accessible and timely medical treatment guaranteed upon the arrival. Disembarkation procedures for arrival by sea, the mechanisms of referral and response of the reception centres are characterised by structural differences at the local level and the involvement of both institutional and non-institutional actors. These factors, together with the absence of standard operating procedures establishing stable and fixed mechanisms for identifying and responding to SGBV at national level, undermine the efforts aimed at ensuring a timely and coordinated response.

The National Commission for the Right to Asylum is seeking to contribute to an effective, coordinated and harmonised response to SGBV, facilitating the rapid identification and assistance of refugees and asylum seekers who have survived serious violence or are vulnerable to violence. To this end, in December 2017, the National Commission of Asylum Law published a circular letter addressed to all the Territorial Commissions in order to solicit adequate interventions in favour of women who survive gender violence, strengthening contacts between the Anti-Violence Centres of the D.I.R.E network operating at national level. UNHCR has also launched a project focused on identifying and supporting people who have survived or are at risk of gender-based violence, in the context of the recognition procedure for international protection.

Calabria is a region where there are no specific rules on SGBV, especially when refugees and asylum seekers are victims. Nevertheless, some official initiatives are carried out by NGOs and associations such as the Memorandum of Understanding signed between the Psychologists' Association of Calabria and UNICEF Calabria for providing psychological assistance to unaccompanied migrant children (UMC), or the creation of clinics providing free health care for migrants focused on detection and assistance to victims of torture and other vulnerable cases, such as that established with a protocol between AUSER, Kasbah NGOs, ASP and the Province of Cosenza.

There are also some projects and practices in relation to specific groups of refugees and asylum seekers that have started recently whose impact is to be evaluated. For example, in 2018 Calabria was one of the regions involved in the IOM Project PROTECT – Preventing Sexual and Gender-Based Violence against Migrant and Strengthening Support to Victims (2019) – which focuses on social and health services for SGBV victims in various regions, in particular for unaccompanied minors. In an area where health services suffer from lack of resources, specific services for migrants, and in particular for unaccompanied minors, are insufficient compared to the number of people arriving in recent years. In addition, other challenges include the fragmented nature of Italy and the rapid transfer at regional and interregional level of children from first reception centres to second reception centres.

For LGBTQ people, in Cosenza, Arci-gay (Association for the Right of LGBTQ People) has implemented the MigrAzioni project, one of seven in Italy focusing on LGBTQ asylum seekers and refugees, which counsels and orientates around 20 people. As one of the coordinators of Arci-gay reported in an interview that the project emerged as a response to a specific need that spontaneously manifested itself two years ago, when refugees and asylum seekers were sent either by lawyers or SPRAR referents to get membership cards to the association in order to 'prove' they belonged to the LGBTQ community at the hearing before the Territorial Commission. Since

this system has been largely abused, it has now become necessary to provide an articulated report into refugees' life stories.

This led to the creation of a proper desk for LGBTQ refugees and asylum seekers, usually sent by SPRAR projects, and to the organisation of a series of social and associative activities involving refugees in an empowerment path involving the Arci-gay association. For children reported to have been victims of SGBV, especially when their sexual orientation was evident, this made them particularly vulnerable.

Based on the collaboration between UNHCR and D.I.R.E. network, the Fondazione Lanzino project tries to intercept refugees and asylum seekers who suffer or have survived domestic and sexual violence. Domestic violence or proximity violence is the most difficult to report: although there are cases of separation as a result of violence along the migration and reception pathways, complaints are rare. Therefore there are no data at national or local level, but rather only qualitative research on limited experiences, as the ones collected in the research PROVIDE – Proximity Violence in Migration Times (Bartholini, 2019).

Since 2011, Calabria has taken ownership of social protection interventions for victims of trafficking and survival sex workers previously managed by various local entities and in particular by the Catholic Church, and coordinates several projects in different provinces. It also takes an active part in a series of interregional and transnational projects on the issue of trafficking, such as adhering to the 'SaviAV – Social Inclusion and Job Integration of Asylum Seekers and Victims' transnational network. In 2018, the region produced a document setting the strategic outlook for Calabria and organised an international conference called 'Doppio Sguardo. La tratta delle donne nigeriane' [Double Look. Trafficking and Nigerian women].

The region's commitment has made it possible to have an offer system that now embraces the entire chain of interventions envisaged by the Equal Opportunities Department at national level: from the harm reduction (with a 'road unit' and the provision of information, orienting and counselling services), to social protection actions (legal advice, psychological support and socio-health assistance). There are also semi-residential and residential reception interventions (around five family homes of first and second housing support) and social inclusion interventions (schooling, professional training courses, as well as activities supporting socio-employment integration through work bursaries and job searching). Although many territories are not covered and only about 10% of the likely victims are actually being reached, this is an area of vulnerability that is being better addressed.

6. Emerging Themes

Regarding the analysis of gender dynamics in integration of migrants, refugees and asylum seekers, the following critical points have been identified and respective recommendations presented:

- The housing management system still reflects the voluntary participation of private individuals and the sensitivity of local reception projects.
- An increase in specialised staff and specific housing integration pathways for migrant and refugee women, especially if they are victims of trafficking, is recommended.
- Regarding educational integration, there is a need for gender-sensitive measures to support the participation and inclusion of migrant women in society.
- Some measures could concern the provision of family balancing measures (babysitting and childcare services overall) and training opportunities for migrant women, including courses to strengthen language skills.
- Compared to men, many women have migrated for family reasons. This can make them dependent on their husbands to find work or obtain residence permits.
- Reducing this dependency in line with the EU guidelines on family reunification and minimising administrative delays in granting residence permits would be crucial.
- Specific services to support self-employment should be designed, not according to the skills already obtained (which are often hard to detect), but by focusing on the work skills needed within the labour market.
- There is a need for specific data both at national and at local level, on the different declinations of SGBV and categories affected.
- There is a low degree of specialisation of NGO workers dealing with refugees that, among other things, prevent women participation and empowerment.
- New qualitative analyses are needed on some aspects of SGBV particularly under-known, as for example domestic violence among refugees or violence against refugees in reception centres or on the consequence of violence on reproductive health.
- Reception centres specifically addressing the need of LGBTQIA refugees are needed. In the case of transgender people, cases of specific violence occur even in reception systems, where there is no adequate knowledge to recognise and interact with transgender refugees.
- Better communication and coordination between different public and private organisations dealing with refugees, and in particular for those affected or particularly vulnerable to violence, is desirable.

Appendix A: Acronyms and Abbreviations

CAS: Extraordinary reception centre	[Centro di accoglienza straordinaria]
CoE: Council of Europe	[Consiglio d'Europa]
COL: Work Orientation Centres	[Centri di Orientamento al Lavoro]
CPI: Employment Centres	[<i>Centri per l'Impiego</i>]
CPIA: Provincial Centres for Adult Education	[Centri Provinciali per l'Istruzione degli Adulti]
OSCAD: Observatory for security against discriminatory acts	[Osservatorio per la sicurezza contro gli atti discriminatori]
INPS: National Social Security Institute	[Istituto nazionale di previdenza sociale]
MIUR: Ministry of Education, University and Research	[Ministero dell'istruzione, Università e ricerca]
SIPROIMI: Protection system for holders of international protection and unaccompanied foreign minors	[Sistema di protezione per titolari di protezione internazionale e per minori stranieri non accompagnati]
SGBV: Sexual and Gender-Based Violence	[Violenza sessuale e di genere]
SPRAR: Protection system for asylum seekers and refugees	[Sistema di protezione per richiedenti asilo e rifugiati]
TUI: Consolidated Immigration Act	[Testo unico Immigrazione]

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